

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA PROMOTION AND SERVICE QUALITY REGARDING PURCHASING DECISIONS AT FITTARA COFFEE SIDOARJO

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received Apr 10, 2024 Revised Apr 20, 2024 Accepted Apr 29, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Social Media Promotion, Service Quality, Purchase Decisions</p>	<p>Currently, in the culinary industry this has happened. Companies now see greater business opportunities through the use of internet media as a promotional tool. With increasingly advanced technology, the internet is no longer a strange thing in product marketing. The company always pays attention to product quality, consumer needs, packaging and effective promotions. Many business promotions are now turning to social media because the majority of internet users in Indonesia are active in the trade and services sectors. Marketing strategies via social media can increase sales without large costs. Consumers also find it easier to get information about the products they want through technology which is part of e-commerce, which is the way companies communicate, promote and sell products via the internet. In Indonesia, in this globalization era, business competition is getting tighter with ongoing technological developments. The aim of conducting this line research is to find out whether knowledge of Promotion, Social Media, Service Quality influences Purchase Decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo. This type of research uses quantitative methods. The population is all buyers who have made transactions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo with a sample size of 100 respondents from distributing questionnaire statements via Google Form. The results obtained state that Social Media Promotion and Service Quality simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo. Testing this hypothesis concluded partially that Social Media Promotion had a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions, and Service Quality had a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p> <div style="text-align: right;"> </div>

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INTRODUCTION

The development of the culinary industry is growing rapidly. When companies obtain business opportunities through the existence of internet media, they use it as a reference for their business promotion. Nowadays, thanks to advances in technology, it is no longer uncommon to use the internet to market industrial products. The internet has great potential so that it can be used as a means of marketing business, so that all companies always focus on the quality of the products offered, customer needs and desires, product packages and promotions offered. Currently, company promotion is moving to the internet, namely to social networks. This is because the majority of internet users in Indonesia are in the retail and service sectors. Marketing strategies through social media promotions can increase sales without the need for expensive marketing campaigns. Customers can also search for information about the products they want to buy. Consumers use technology to fulfill their daily needs. This can be seen from the increasing use of information technology sites by consumers to meet their information needs. The act of marketing products or services using an Internet platform is called e-commerce. Electronic marketing is a form of electronic commerce marketing, which includes activities in which companies communicate, promote, and sell their goods and services on the Internet. As we know, Indonesia is a developing country. In this era of globalization, the business world has become very competitive. This competition follows ever-increasing technological developments and, rightly or wrongly, drives system changes around the world. According to a study by the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers (APJII), the number of internet users in 2022-2023o will reach 215.63 million people. In the previous period, the number of internet users was only 210.03 million, showing an increase of 2.67%. Thus, 78.19% of Indonesia's total population of 275.77 million people were internet users.

According to (Rulli Nasrullah, 2017) social media has become an online platform where users can express themselves and interact, collaborate, share and communicate with other users to create virtual social networks. The three aspects of socializing on social media are celebration, communication, and collaboration. Social networks facilitate the exchange of information between users and do so with honesty, integrity, trust and responsibility. Using social media promotion strategies will increase sales.

According to (Ismail, Haron, Ibrahim, 2006). Service quality is important for any business as it is an after-sales review and when service quality is met, customer loyalty increases. One way to achieve service quality is that it is important for companies to improve the quality of their own services. Service quality and customer satisfaction are important considerations for improvement.

According to (Yusuf, 2021) consumer purchasing decisions are said to be a process of evaluating various products to choose one of them. So it can be concluded that decisions by buyers are an aspect of consumer behavior in determining decisions before and after purchasing a product in fulfilling their desires and needs. The results of this process are actions that consumers can choose.

Based on the description of the causes of the problem described above, the author wants to conduct further research regarding "The Influence of Social Media Promotion and Service Quality of Fittara Sidoarjo Coffee on Purchasing Decisions".

HYPOTHESIS

Figure 1 Basic Framework of Thought
Source: Processed by the Author, 2024

1. First Hypothesis

Ho: No There is the influence of social media promotion on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

Ha: There is an influence of social media promotion on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

2. Second Hypothesis

Ho: No There is an influence of service quality on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

Ha: There is an influence of service quality on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

3. Third Hypothesis

Ho: No There is an influence of social media promotion and service quality on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

Ha: There is an influence of social media promotion and service quality on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach. Through associative research, this research aims to understand the significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. This research uses probability sampling techniques with purposive sampling where the sample requires certain considerations, namely by meeting the criteria "consumers have purchased products twice or more at Shopee in the Surabaya area". The data collection technique used in the research is using an electronic questionnaire and a Likert scale is used as a measurement scale. The questionnaire used is an electronic closed questionnaire. Electronic questionnaires are distributed online using Google Forms. First, the questionnaire tests the validity and reliability of the statement items, after passing, then distribute the questionnaire to obtain data. The data obtained will be analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis and hypothesis testing which includes t-test (partial), F-test (simultaneous), and coefficient of determination (R²).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity test

The validity of a questionnaire is assessed using a validity test. The validity of the questionnaire is determined if the calculated r exceeds the r table. Each instrument was evaluated for validity using the product moment Pearson correlation approach.

Figure 2 Validity Test Results

Variabel		R hitung	R tabel	Kesimpulan
Promosi Media Sosial (X1)	P1	0.724	0.361	VALID
	P2	0.646	0.361	VALID
	P3	0.615	0.361	VALID
	P4	0.816	0.361	VALID
	P5	0.637	0.361	VALID
Kualitas Pelayanan (X2)	P6	0.799	0.361	VALID
	P7	0.734	0.361	VALID
	P8	0.692	0.361	VALID
	P9	0.762	0.361	VALID
	P10	0.634	0.361	VALID
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	P11	0.789	0.361	VALID
	P12	0.612	0.361	VALID
	P13	0.695	0.361	VALID
	P14	0.662	0.361	VALID
	P15	0.573	0.361	VALID
	P16	0.502	0.361	VALID

Source: SPSS 23 Output (2024)

The validity test results above are consistent with the respondents' perceptions of each variable statement Social Media Promotion (X1), Service Quality (X2), and Purchase Decisions (Y). Specifically, all calculated r values $>$ r table from 30 respondents' answers as a validity test were greater than 0.361.

Reliability Test

Assessing the reliability of an instrument means finding out whether the instrument regularly provides the same results when used again. If the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of an instrument is more than 0.600, then the instrument is considered reliable.

Figure 3 Reliability Test Results

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Angka Pemanding	Keterangan
Promosi Media Sosial (X1)	0.772	0.600	RELIABEL
Kualitas Pelayanan (X2)	0.785	0.600	RELIABEL
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0.757	0.600	RELIABEL

Source: SPSS 23 Output, (2024)

Reliability test, which describes the Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.600. Hallini indicated that the variables Sales Promotion (X1), Shopping Lifestyle (X2), and

Impulsive Buying (Y) were considered reliable and would provide consistent results even if tested repeatedly.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

$$IY = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 6.818 + 0.472X_1 + 0.373X_2$$

- a. The constant value (α) is 6.818, so it can be interpreted that if the Social Media Promotion Variable (X1) and the Service Quality Variable (X2) are equal to 0 (constant) then the Purchase Decision Variable (Y) will increase by 6.818
- b. The regression coefficient value $b_1(X_1) = 0.472$, meaning that if the Social Media Promotion Variable (X1) increases by one unit assuming the Service Quality Variable (X2) is equal to 0 (constant) then the Purchase Decision variable (Y) will increase by 0.472.
- c. The regression coefficient value $b_2(X_2) = 0.373$, meaning that if the Service Quality variable (X2) increases by one unit assuming the Social Media Promotion variable (X1) is equal to 0 (constant) then the Purchase Decision Variable (Y) will increase by 0.373.

Hypothesis testing

t Test (Partial)

To show how the independent variables sales promotion and shopping lifestyle influence the dependent variable impulse buying. A significance level of 0.05 or 5% is used to test the hypothesis.

Figure 4 t Test (Partial)

Coefficients						
a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.818	1.836		3.714	0.000
	Promosi Media Sosial	0.472	0.103	0.433	4.604	0.000
	Kualitas Pelayanan	0.373	0.112	0.313	3.331	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN

Source: SPSS output, 2024

$$T \text{ table} = (a/2 : nk-1)$$

a = significant (0.05)

k = number of independent variables

n = Number of samples used

So in this study it can be observed that the significant value (α) is 5% (0.05) with $df = 100 - 3 = 97$, the t table is 1.998. The results of hypothesis testing can be stated as follows.

1. First Hypothesis

It is known that the sig.m value for the influence of kX1 on kY is 0.000, less than $l < 0.05$ and the t-calculated value is $4,604 > \text{table } 1.998$, so it can be concluded that Hal is accepted and Ho is rejected, which means that the Promotion variable, Social Media (X1) has an influence on the Purchase Decision variable (Y).

2. Second Hypothesis

It is known that the result of the sig.m value for the influence of kX1 on kY is 0.000less than <0.05 land the calculated value is $3.331 > \text{table } 1.998$, so it can be concluded that Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected, which means that the Social Media Promotion variable (X1) has an effect on the purchase decision variable (Y).

Simultaneous Test (F)

To determine whether the independent variable has the same effect on the dependent variable, the F test is applied with a significance of less than 0.05 and the F-calculation is higher than the F table.

Figure 5 Simultaneous Test (F)

ANOVA						
a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	610.827	2	305.413	39.420	.000 ^b
	Residual	751.533	97	7.748		
	Total	1362.360	99			
a. Dependent Variable: KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Promosi Media Sosial, Kualitas Pelayanan						

Source: SPSS output, 2024

The results of the F test to find the F table are:

$$df = n - k - 1$$

Information :

n = Number of Samples

k = Number of Independent Variables

So :

$$= 2 ; 100 - 2$$

$$= 2 ; 98$$

$$= 3.89$$

So the F table at $\alpha = 5\%$ (0.05) results in a kF-table of k3.89 with an F-count of 39.420.

So with F calculate that

higher than F table and the significance value of 0.000 is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that Social Media Promotion and Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions have a significant influence on purchasing products at Shopee.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

Figure 6 Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.670 ^a	0.448	0.437	2.783
a. Predictors: (Constant), Promosi Media Sosial, Kualitas Pelayanan				

Source: SPSS output, 2024

The R² (R Square) value is 0.448 or 44.8% of the R Square result or coefficient of determination. So it shows that the influence of the independent variables Social Media Promotion (X1) and Service Quality (X2) has an influence on the dependent variable purchasing decisions (Y) of 0.448 or 44.8% while the remaining 55.2% is influenced by other factors.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research that the researcher discussed regarding "The Influence of Social Media Promotion and Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo", the researcher concluded as follows:

- a. The Social Media Promotion variable on Purchasing Decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo can be partially concluded as having a positive and significant influence. Which means that the more people promote Fittara Coffee, the more purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo will increase. The results from respondents stated that the highest score or value was obtained from the promotion frequency indicator with the statement "Fittara Coffee always carries out various promotions via social media"
- b. The variable Service Quality on Purchasing Decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo can be partially concluded as having a positive and significant influence. Which means that by implementing good service quality at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo, purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo will increase. The results from respondents stated that the highest score or value was obtained by the Emphaty indicator with the statement "Fittara Coffee always behaves politely with customers"
- c. The variables Social Media Promotion and Service Quality simultaneously (together) have a significant positive influence on purchasing decisions at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo. Due to the highest perception of Promotion and Service, it will be easier for a consumer to make a decision to buy at Fittara Coffee Sidoarjo

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